

EMILY

DIEGO

JEFFREY

JEFFREY

VIRGIL

CONTRIBUTORS

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SYNOPSIS

Forever alone in a crowd, failed comedian Arthur Fleck seeks connection as he walks the streets of Gotham City. Arthur wears two masks -- the one he paints for his day job as a clown, and the guise he projects in a futile attempt to feel like he's part of the world around him. Isolated, bullied and disregarded by society, Fleck begins a slow descent into madness as he transforms into the criminal mastermind known as the Joker.

THE FILMMAKERS

TODD PHILLIPS

DIRECTOR

born December 20, 1970, is an American film director, producer, screenwriter, and actor. His early career primarily involved directing comedy films, including *Old School* (2003), *Starsky & Hutch* (2004) and *The Hangover Trilogy* (2009, 2011, and 2013). He also co-wrote the satirical comedy film *Borat* (2006) which was also nominated for Best Adapted Screenplay. Phillips later co-wrote and directed the psychological thriller film *Joker* (2019), which premiered at the 76th Venice International Film Festival where it received the top prize, the Golden Lion. *Joker* went on to earn him Academy Award nominations for Best Picture, Best Director, and Best Adapted Screenplay, alongside his co-writer Scott Silver.

FILMOGRAPHY

Joker	2019
War Dogs	2016
The Hangover Part III	2013
The Hangover Part II	2011
Due Date	2010
The Hangover	2009
The More Things Change...	2008
School for Scoundrels	2006
Starsky & Hutch: A Last Look	2004
Starsky & Hutch	2004
Old School	2003
Road Trip	2000
Bittersweet Motel	2000
Frat House	1998
Hated: GG Allin & the Murder Junkies	1993

LAWRENCE SHER

CINEMATOGRAPHER

Black Adam	(pre-production)	Dan in Real Life	2007
The Starling	(post-production)	Cavemen (TV Series)	2007
Wear a Mask, Bat Dick	2020	Andy Barker, P.I. (TV)	2007
Daughter	2020	When a Man Falls	2007
Most Likely to Succeed	2019	When the Nines Roll Over	2006
Becoming Joker	2019	Grilled	2006
Joker	2019	Life of the Party	2005
Godzilla: King of the Monsters	2019	The Dukes of Hazzard	2005
I Don't Want to Be Your Love	2019	The Chumscrubber	2005
Cheeky Plates for Target	2017	Club Dread	2004
War Dogs	2016	Garden State	2004
Wish I Was Here	2014	Legally Blonde (TV Movie)	2003
The Hangover Part III	2013	Emmett's Mark	2002
The Dictator	2012	The Wonderful World of Disney	2001
The Big Year	2011	The Facts of Life Reunion	2001
Enlightened (Pilot)	2011	Kissing Jessica Stein	2001
The Hangover Part II	2011	Boxing's Been Good to Me	2000
Paul	2011	A Better Way to Die	2000
Due Date	2010	Shark Attack (TV Movie)	1999
The Eastmans	2009	12 Stops on the Road to Nowhere	1999
The Hangover	2009	On the Border	1998
I Love You, Man	2009	Courting Courtney	1997
Trucker	2008	Captain Jack	1995
The Promotion	2008	The Return of Wes Lauren	1992

**MARK
FRIEDBERG**
PRODUCTION DESIGNER

The Underground Railroad (TV)	2020	Identity	2003
Joker	2019	Far from Heaven	2002
If Beale Street Could Talk	2018	Kate & Leopold	2001
The Upside	2017	Hopewell (TV Movie)	2000
Wonderstruck	2017	Pollock	2000
Billy Lynn's Long Halftime Walk	2016	Autumn in New York	2000
Paterson	2016	Ride with the Devil	1999
The Audition (Short)	2015	Runaway Bride	1999
Selma	2014	Poodle Springs (TV Movie)	1998
The Amazing Spider-Man 2	2014	Sex and the City (TV Series)	1998
Noah	2014	Destination Anywhere (Video)	1997
New Year's Eve	2011	The Ice Storm	1997
Mildred Pierce (TV)	2011	I'm Not Rappaport	1996
The Beaver	2011	Kama Sutra: A Tale of Love	1996
Morning Glory	2010	Duke of Groove (TV Short)	1996
The Tempest	2010	The Perez Family	1995
State of Play	2009	The Vernon Johns Story (TV Movie)	1994
Tenderness	2009	The Ballad of Little Jo	1993
Synecdoche, New York	2008	The Adventures of Pete & Pete (TV)	1992
Across the Universe	2007	The Paint Job	1992
The Darjeeling Limited	2007	In the Soup	1992
The Producers	2005	Walking the Dog (Short)	1991
Broken Flowers	2005	A Matter of Degrees	1990
The Life Aquatic with Steve Zissou	2004	Comedy's Dirtiest Dozen	1988
Coffee and Cigarettes	2003		

JEFF GROTH

EDITOR

Cherry	(post-production)	- Basic Genealogy	2010
Joker	2019	- Comparative Religion	2009
Valley of the Boom (TV Series)	2019	- Debate 109	2009
- Part 4: priority inversion	2019	- Introduction to Statistics	2009
- Part 3: agile method	2019	Religulous (Documentary)	2008
- Part 2: pseudocode	2019	Man Maid	2008
Deadly Class (TV Series)	2018	Tori & Dean: Inn Love (TV)	2007
- Reagan Youth	2018	- Let's Go Have a Baby	2007
Office Christmas Party	2016	- What About the Guests?	2007
War Dogs	2016	- I Love a Party	2007
Entourage	2015	- Too Pregnant	2007
The Wedding Ringer	2015	- Paint on the Extensions!	2007
The Hangover Part III	2013	- B&B or Bust	2007
40 (TV Short)	2012	- Too Shaky for the Baby	2007
Project X	2012	- Dump Everything You Can Dump!	2007

Our Show (TV Movie)	2010	So Goes the Nation (Documentary)	2006
Entourage (TV) (12 episodes)	2008 - 2010	Pickled (Short)	2005
- Sniff Sniff Gang Bang	2010	Christmas in Tinseltown (Short)	2004
- Bottoms Up	2010	L.A. 10,000 B.C. (TV)	2004
- Buzzed	2010	Tag Along with Will Ferrell (Short)	2004
- Scared Straight	2009	Seventy-Seven Below (Short)	2004
- Berried Alive	2009	The Clay Man (Short)	2004
- Murphy's Lie	2009	Seven Days (Short)	2004
- Fore	2009	Minnesota Nice (Short)	2004
- Amongst Friends	2009	Whether You Like It or Not: The	
- Play'n with Fire	2008	Story of Hedwig (Video documentary)	2003
- Pie	2008	Behind the Scenes of 'John Q'	
- First Class Jerk	2008	(Video documentary short)	2002
- Tree Trippers	2008	The Politics of Fur	2002
Community (TV) (5 episodes)	2009-2010	Riffed	2001
- Beginner Pottery	2010	Afraid of Everything	1999

STORY'S GENERAL THEME

ALTHOUGH THERE ARE A HANDFUL OF THEMES THREADED THROUGHOUT THE NARRATIVE, SUCH AS TRAUMA, MENTAL ILLNESS, THE FAILURE OF THE STATE, SOCIAL WARFARE, ANARCHY, THE GENERAL THEME OF THE JOKER IS TRANSFORMATION, THE GIVING IN TO EXCRUCIATING CIRCUMSTANCES— WHEN RESISTANCE BECOMES ACCEPTANCE. IT IS A CHARACTERS TRANSFORMATION INTO A TRUE VILLAIN. ARTHUR FLECK PUTS IT BEST WHEN HE STATES, “I USED TO THINK THAT MY LIFE WAS A TRAGEDY. BUT NOW I REALIZE...IT’S A COMEDY.”

WHY SO SERIOUS?

A DISTINCTIVE FEATURE OR DOMINANT IDEA IN AN ARTISTIC OR LITERARY COMPOSITION.

MOTIFS

ARCHWAYS

ARKHAM STATE H

There are archways everywhere - in the city of Gotham, in the entryway to the apartment building, as we enter Arkham hospital. Symbolically, arches represent passageways, and transition. They're something that a person passes through - and connects the outside to the inside. Each time Arthur passes through them, we inch closer and closer to his discovery of who he is, and his embrace of being Joker.

BLOOD

Blood is everywhere in Joker. It's a visceral film, one that engrosses the audience in the experiences of Arthur Fleck and his transformation. We see blood numerous times as we progress more and more into his descent into madness and the reality of who he is. Blood marks his first act of violence in the killing of the three men on the subway as the train car is painted with the blood of his victims.

When he kills Randall, blood penetrates his skin, contrasted with the stark white of his face paint as he slowly becomes Joker. Perhaps most significant is the bloody smile he paints on his face as the rioters cheer him on at the end of the film. As he walks down the hallway in the last scene, the blood of the social worker marks the white floor.

CLOWNS & SMILES

The idea of clowns and a 'smile' are recurring motifs throughout *Joker* that walk hand in hand in the development of Arthur's character and journey to become the figure we all know him to be. It's a concept that brings to life a visual mask and facade, and hammers into the audience's mind this idea of 'putting on a happy face,' which is what Arthur at the beginning is told his life is supposed to be for others.

Clowns are a visual metaphor, as he desperately tries to create laughter, even in bad situations. As he descends into madness and becomes a truer version of himself, there's more smiles, more irony in his actions with others (i.e. the destruction of the sign on his way out of the clown company), and more genuine smiles on his own face as he becomes Joker.

At the end, we see him literally paint a red smile with blood on his face as he greets the angry crowd, at that moment the most authentically himself and the happiest he's been, because for a moment he feels seen by society and appreciated.

Don't Forget To
Smile

CHARLIE CHAPLIN (THE TRAMP)

We catch glimpses of Charlie Chaplin and the character of The Tramp throughout *Joker*, solidifying the idea of trying to be someone else, adopting a persona, and themes of social class separation and misunderstanding. In the opening scene, Arthur is dressed as a clown for work, comically tossing a sign outside of a closing store. Even after he's beaten by a group of boys, he hits the button in his sleeve that dispenses water from the flower on his jacket, an attempt to find a sliver of humor in the situation. This mimics Charlie Chaplin's character - who attempts to handle situations as a gentleman despite his poor social status. The Chaplin film *Modern Times* is also prevalent at the fundraiser for Thomas Wayne as tensions rise in the city.

CORRIDORS

In a similar manner to the staircase, corridors also frequent the frame in *Joker*, and almost always in the same manner. It's a driving force in the inevitability of Arthur's transformation into the Joker. We're almost always put behind him as he marches down hallways and corridors, leading lines pointing to one vanishing point, one central spot for him to end. There's no two paths in the woods for him to choose, just one destination. It's only broken right at the end moment when he is fully himself and in a comedic burst of energy he teases the Arkham guards, racing side to side before disappearing into the light.

CURTAINS

Curtains are an important piece of *Joker*, representing the gradual unveiling of Arthur's transformation over the course of the film. Curtains are present at pivotal moments - hinting at the reveal that's going to happen at the end of the film. We see Arthur practicing his entrance to the Murray Franklin show, an impromptu curtain strung up across the doorway of the apartment. We see curtains surrounding the hospital bed where his mother lies, both shrouding and preparing him for the reveal of his true character. And finally, we have the Murray Franklin show itself, where he shows the world that he's Joker.

DANCING

Dance is something we see consistently throughout the film, although it's meaning grows darker and darker as we delve further into Arthur's character and conscience. At the beginning, dance is something he does to fulfill his character when he's working as a clown. It's something he does to try to bring joy to people. As he changes, dance becomes something more. It becomes a reflection of how he sees his life as more of a comedy than a tragedy.

Dance follows all of his darker moments - and as he recognizes his true nature the dance slows down and becomes more of a reflective, introspective movement as he dances in the bathroom after killing the three men on the subway, when he fully commits to his new persona and truer self as Joker after dyeing his hair green, after the satisfaction of killing Randall and embracing his true self, as he is idolized by crowds of people in clown masks, and after he kills the social worker at Arkham in the last scene, bathed in light and the revelation of finally knowing and embracing who he is.

MIRRORS

Mirrors are another thing that are everywhere in this film. We open on a slow crawl on Arthur Fleck as he applies makeup for his job as a clown, moving the camera around to see his face in a forced smile. Mirrors occur time and time again, reminding us that this is an internal struggle of Arthur trying to come to terms with his identity, and ultimately creating one of his own. Mirrors are the one device in which someone can look and only see themselves. They're a symbol of truth. It's no different than how Arthur sees himself; a loner, cast out by society, forced to deal with his own pain and mental illness.

As he asserts his identity more and more, and accepts the truth of where he comes from and his past, he becomes more confident in front of the mirrors - arms outstretched after killing the men on the subway, laughing and dancing as he dyes his hair green.

STAIRS

The infamous Magic Hour scene from 'Joker' takes place on the staircase, but the use of stairs is also prevalent throughout the film as well. At first, stairs represent the slow trudge of Arthur's daily struggle - his commute to work and home, this almost infinite staircase leading to the dark apartment building in which he cares for his mother. For the first half of the film, all we see is him moving up the stairs - climbing but never really ascending.

It's only once Arthur starts to discover more about his own life and self that we start to descend stairs. He moves down them after stealing the records from the Arkham clerk, stopping on a landing to discover the truth about his past and the adoption and abuse. It's only when he fully is revealed in Joker form that he fully descends the stairs in the magnificent dance scene.

TRANSPARENT BARRIERS

One thing that frequents the frame of 'Joker' is transparent barriers. Arthur is constantly put on the other side of bars, gates, and mesh barriers that literally and metaphorically place him on the other side of society. He's a self-described loner, and we witness this as time and time again people fail to understand him for who he is. This also echoes the theme of class difference in Gotham.

We see him spying on Sophie through a chainlink fence. We see Arthur outside the gates of Wayne Manor, trying to connect with Bruce and access Thomas Wayne. We see him literally placed in a phone booth box when he's fired, and he tries to break through by banging his head against the glass and try to break into society. We see him fail to get into the hospital after the confrontation with the police. We see him trying to find answers from Arkham Hospital with the clerk on the other side. We see him in the back of the police car, and even as he gazes out the windows gleefully at people in clown masks, he's still separated by a pane of glass.

This all remarks on his desire to be seen, but the inability of society to really do so.

POINT OF VIEW PROPOSAL

STORY: A MENTALLY ILL LONER IS HAUNTED BY HIS PAST AND PRESENT CIRCUMSTANCES IN THE GRITTY CHAOS OF A BIG CITY. HE REACHES A BREAKING POINT AND TRANSFORMS INTO A VIGILANTE KILLER.

POINT-OF-VIEW:
DARK, VIOLENT, AND DRAMATIC WHERE THE DIVIDE BETWEEN RICH AND POOR CRUMBLES UNDER THE UPRISING OF THE MASSES. THE STATE HAS FAILED THE PEOPLE AND WHATEVER CRUMMY LIFE ANYONE CAN SCRATCH OUT IS CRUSHED BY THE WEIGHT OF GROWING RESTLESSNESS AND DARKNESS.

I used to think my life was a tragedy, but now I realize, it's a **FUCKING COMEDY !!!**

CRASH!
SMASH!

SPACE: A LOT OF FLAT SPACE VIA SHALLOW DEPTH OF FIELD AND CLOSEUPS WITH OPEN SPACE TO EMPHASIS THE INTERNAL WORLD AND TENSION ARTHUR FLECK IS LIVING. DEEP SPACE IS USED TO SHOW THE SEEMINGLY ENDLESS URBAN GRIT OF GOTHAM CITY.

STORY LOCATION:
GOTHAM CITY
REMINISCENT OF 1980'S NYC

**FORGIVE MY LAUGHTER,
I HAVE A CONDITION.**

yeaahhh!
LOVE IT!
LOVE IT!

yeaahhh!
LOVE IT! LOVE IT!

THE VISUAL COMPONENT PLAN

- Line and Shape: Heavy use of diagonals emphasizing the chaotic, tense world of Gotham City. Thick, bold vertical and horizontal lines are used throughout to paint a prison cell environment whether indoors or outdoors.

- Tone: Dark shots with heavy contrast are favored that show a lot of texture. Shadows wrap character's faces with medium to high contrast ratios. Most of the film's action takes place at night or in dimly lit interiors.

- Color: Cool colors such as blues dominate the film with complementary touches of yellow and orange. Colors are bold and saturated as a superficial facade to the dark reality teeming underneath.

- Movement: Camera movement favors handheld, cinema verité style punctuated by moments of steadiness via tripod or dolly track use. The handheld aesthetic gives an authentic impression to the film akin to watching a documentary as we explore and empathize with Arthur's crushing circumstances.

- Rhythm: Longer takes are employed during moments where Arthur is thinking or dancing. We enter his internal state and either reflect on it as he sits against the glass of a bus or dances away the murder of three businessmen. Outdoor scenes are composed towards medium to wide angle to capture the overbearing, gloomy cityscape. Such scenes will contrast via editing with more intimate closeup portraits.

COLOR SCRIPT

Joker takes primary colors (Red, Blue, and Yellow) and pits them against one another to each tell us as the audience something different about Arthur as we follow his journey. They work against one another and in unison, often bleeding into the same scenes and visually representing Arthur's internal struggle.

Color progresses in such an interesting way through Joker. It begins as this muted world in white Arthur is depressed and struggling to come to terms with his own being. As he understands more about himself and descends into the Joker, the colors become more vibrant versions of themselves, much like Joker becomes a more vibrant and understood version of Arthur.

RED

Red in Joker is fleeting but impactful. It's not as prevalent as the blues and yellows, but emphasizes pivotal points in Arthur's journey. On one hand, red is representative of love - Sophie wears red in the elevator, hinting at Arthur's affections, and the red lamps of the comedy club depict Arthur's desire to be a stand-up comedian and his love for making people laugh. The red also symbolizes truth, as he discovers his adoption in the red folder of Arkham's records. When Arthur makes the decision to embrace his identity as Joker, he dons a bright red suit, as he becomes more and more accepting of who he is and cares less what society thinks.

HEX: #922413

HEX: #B9512C

HEX: #D5858B

HEX: #A1311C

HEX: #CC885B

HEX: #C57546

HEX: #80170E

HEX: #BD4965

HEX: #4B0908

HEX: #971D25

HEX: #C04A74

HEX: #200B0A

HEX: #261F11

HEX: #524236

HEX: #4D2417

HEX: #362321

HEX: #76491C

HEX: #772D12

HEX: #38241E

HEX: #562D33

HEX: #4D2417

HEX: #311810

HEX: #2A1B0F

HEX: #5D2E30

HEX: #511B18

HEX: #5B1F1A

HEX: #704E31

HEX: #60503D

HEX: #C8B485

HEX: #8D6849

HEX: #592D2F

HEX: #4F2A2E

HEX: #AE833A

HEX: #2B4132

HEX: #12221E

HEX: #245754

HEX: #6E2014

HEX: #9C2022

HEX: #B64B21

HEX: #D59BA9

HEX: #74A79D

HEX: #6C1B12

HEX: #1D120F

HEX: #4D291D

HEX: #461C14

HEX: #561D16

HEX: #1E4546

HEX: #394E22

HEX: #333018

HEX: #414C29

HEX: #356745

HEX: #171C17

HEX: #401A12

HEX: #522B15

HEX: #812D26

HEX: #795927

HEX: #2B3A3D

HEX: #0B120F

HEX: #89634A

HEX: #284C59

BLUE

Blue is representative of Gotham and everything that works against Arthur. It's cold, chilling, and depressed, much like the city itself. It's also representative of Arthur's lack of belonging, and the failure of social services to care for him. When he trudges through the city, he's enveloped by blue. The only warm colors (yellows) we see are when he returns home, to a place he's safe. The lack of understanding that casts him out of the world is shown by blue - the blue of the office of the therapist, the blue jacket of the woman who doesn't understand he's trying to entertain her son, and the blue worn by the people Arthur kills, like the men on the subway, and Randall. When Arthur is at a low, he climbs into the blue light of the fridge, fully enveloped by it, and then swallowed by darkness.

HEX: #16342C

HEX: #0A1C1F

HEX: #102420

HEX: #0F201F

HEX: #0E1F1D

HEX: #1F4536

HEX: #264037

HEX: #74BAA5

HEX: #193F45

HEX: #509D97

HEX: #367763

HEX: #89C7A7

HEX: #102939

HEX: #041118

HEX: #2F6875

HEX: #6CC1B6

HEX: #46525F

HEX: #0A243C

HEX: #071923

HEX: #225464

HEX: #22272C

HEX: #113247

HEX: #244B4E

HEX: #3C6E6C

HEX: #0C282E

HEX: #255651

HEX: #132727

HEX: #11D4957

HEX: #335F50

HEX: #0E2827

YELLOW

Yellow is representative of both madness but also Arthur as a human being as we follow him on this journey to become authentically himself. The warm yellow-oranges symbolize the places he feels safe, and also how he identifies (by the dark muted yellow ochre sweater he wears for much of the film). There's a solitary yellow light outside of his apartment building, yellow walls in the lobby, and yellow-orange lights once he gets inside. The yellows also represent a warning of what's coming - and who Arthur will become. The walls of Arkham are yellow - his irrational behavior and action when he steals the folder with the truth about his mother and tension skyrocketed by the fact that he's surrounded by bright yellow. As Arthur becomes more himself and visually and psychologically accepts the identity of Joker, he trades his muted sweater for a bright yellow vest.

HEX: #BFAD48

HEX: #7E531F

HEX: #888E72

HEX: #BFB46F

HEX: #D4D7A4

HEX: #635E22

HEX: #766527

HEX: #433F15

HEX: #667449

HEX: #E9EBBB

HEX: #7C4D1F

HEX: #635225

HEX: #8D6E2E

HEX: #B4A26A

HEX: #7C7837

HEX: #A7B885

HEX: #E2EED2

HEX: #5C5C31

BLUE + YELLOW

The blues and yellows that are constantly at odds with Arthur's identity collide at several pivotal points in the film and represent his internal struggle. Whenever he's humiliated, or enveloped by negative emotion, we see both blue and yellow present. The boys who beat him up at the beginning of the film wear blue and yellow. His boss's office is blue and yellow, as he's ridiculed for being who he is. That combination of primary colors strike us at those pivotal moments, and pit Arthur against society in a series of clashes. When he loses power, the blue becomes more apparent, but when he takes that power back, we're left with an intense greenish yellow.

HEX: #204851

HEX: #0B1D1C

HEX: #1B3834

HEX: #57573F

HEX: #CCCB9F

HEX: #B7996D

HEX: #392F19

HEX: #243535

HEX: #5E5635

HEX: #5B6E71

HEX: #C6DAC8

HEX: #BCA05B

HEX: #0E2C2F

HEX: #2B6159

HEX: #BEAD4C

HEX: #1F453E

HEX: #1F453E

HEX: #556843

HEX: #2D6A6F

HEX: #1F4E5C

HEX: #A17148

HEX: #7ED1C3

HEX: #255B6C

HEX: #0B2842

HEX: #3A554C

HEX: #83A68D

HEX: #3E453A

HEX: #D3D1A8

HEX: #AA9E79

HEX: #546C5F

GREEN

Green is representative of one thing in this film - death. Arthur is swallowed by green light on the subway before he kills the three men, and the same thing happens when he kills his mother at the hospital. Bruce Wayne's parents are killed by a man in green, connecting Arthur and Bruce's fates. Murray Franklin's stage is subtly dressed with the green of plants - hinting at what's to come. The men who pull him from the cop car also wear green, and as he becomes a symbol of violence, he dyes his hair a vibrant green as well. While green normally symbolizes life, the themes of Joker and the inability of society to understand who Arthur is turn the color green on its head by associating it with death.

HEX: #13261A

HEX: #586938

HEX: #504113

HEX: #326A28

HEX: #264F3A

HEX: #60643A

HEX: #182717

HEX: #3F6049

HEX: #0D130D

HEX: #69756B

HEX: #85A085

HEX: #798A7A

HEX: #CEDFC0

HEX: #26352B

HEX: #9EC19C

HEX: #1F4745

HEX: #30451E

HEX: #223320

HEX: #3A3D3B

HEX: #99C2A4

HEX: #485E58

HEX: #456A65

HEX: #A2C3AD

A vintage movie camera is shown in a close-up, low-angle shot. The camera is illuminated by a warm, golden light, likely from a lamp. The viewfinder at the top shows the words "PICTURE" and "START" in a stylized font. A film strip is visible, partially unspooled and passing through the camera's mechanism. The camera has various dials, buttons, and a lens assembly. The background is a plain, light-colored wall.

MATCH CUT BREAKDOWN

FRAME MATCH

FRAME & LIGHTING MATCH

EYELINE, FRAME & LIGHTING MATCH

ACTION & LIGHTING MATCH

ACTION & LIGHTING MATCH

ACTION & LIGHTING MATCH

ACTION & LIGHTING MATCH

LIGHTING MATCH

EDITORIAL RHYTHM

1:19:50 - 1:22:12

After learning the truth about his past and how his mother lied to him his whole life Arthur to the hospital to confront and kill his mother.

VISUAL
STRUCTURE
GRAPHS

Wayne Double Murder

Waltham City Herald CITY EDITION

Hue

Time Stamps
(Hour & Minutes)

Time Stamps
(Hour & Minutes)

THOMAS WAYNE MURDERED! PROMINENT DOCTOR & WIFE SLAIN IN ROBBERY

Homage Paid To Red Cross By President

UNIDENTIFIED GUNMAN LEAVES CHILD UNHARMED

NON-COINCIDENCE

TONE

CONINCIDENCE

Time Stamps
(Hour & Minutes)

PICTURES WITH TIMELINE

0:02

0:04

0:06

0:08

0:10

0:12

0:14

0:16

0:18

0:20

0:22

0:24

0:26

0:28

0:30

0:32

0:34

0:36

0:38

0:40

0:42

0:44

0:46

0:48

0:50

0:52

0:54

0:56

0:58

1:00

1:02

1:04

1:06

1:08

1:10

1:12

1:14

1:16

1:18

1:20

1:22

1:24

1:26

1:28

1:30

1:32

1:34

1:36

1:38

1:40

1:42

1:44

1:46

1:48

1:50

1:52

1:54

1:56

1:58

2:00

END CREDITS